

HeSANDA for Health Cohorts

PROJECT SHAPING - WORKSHOP REPORT

Summary

A series of 3 online workshops were held by ARDC as part of co-designing the scope of new projects and to help identify potential project partners for the [HeSANDA for Health Cohorts program](#). The workshops were open for public registration and were advertised through ARDC's communication channels and mailing lists, including to existing partners and those that had participated in [previous consultation with health cohort studies](#).

The goal of the workshops was to start developing a common understanding about the HeSANDA for Health Cohort Studies program and the key concepts and issues that would need to be addressed by ARDC and its project partners in the forthcoming program.

This document contains details of the workshops and summaries of the feedback received from the participants.

WORKSHOP DETAILS

Workshop 1

Purpose

The 1st workshop sought feedback to inform ARDC's decisions on the following:

- The kinds of research that the HeSANDA for Health Cohorts program should facilitate
- The 1st program goal of making health cohort studies & their data assets discoverable in Health Data Australia
- The kinds of activities & contributors required to help achieve that goal

Date

30 July 2024

Registrations/attendance

Registrations 74 | Attendance 54

Method

Following an initial presentation, attendees participated in 3 interactive discussions described below. Participants were provided with an overview of the workshop and discussion topics prior to attending.

1. Group Discussion - What kinds of research can be done with shared health cohort study data?

Participants were asked the following questions via a Mentimeter poll. The facilitator invited some participants to speak to their responses to provide additional information.

- What kinds of projects could you do with shared data? What kinds of research would you do by pooling data from different cohort studies?
- Is there research you could do by combining clinical trial and health cohort data?

2. Breakout Session 1 - What information should be included in a catalogue of health cohort study data?

Participants were asked the following questions in small group breakout rooms. Responses were captured in a shared Google Doc.

- Information requirements: What information would be useful to you if you were searching for health cohort study data? What is essential to you? Are there items in the table that are irrelevant?

- Feasibility: Where do you currently record/publish this information? If there's information you don't record or publish, what would you need to change to start recording it?

3. Breakout Session 2 - Key project activities & contributors

Participants were presented with a [high-level draft set of project activities and contributors](#) and asked the following questions. Responses were captured in a shared Google Doc.

- What would you add or change to make this a complete and coherent set of activities?
- Who from your cohort studies would need to be involved in these activities for them to be successful?
- Outside of your group, who are the broader set of stakeholders that should be involved to make this a true national data initiative?

Workshop 2

Purpose

The 2nd workshop sought feedback to inform ARDC's decisions on the following:

- The criteria for selecting which health cohort studies should be the focus or priority of the program
- The purpose and initial considerations for enabling measure-level discovery of cohort data

Date

15 Aug 2024

Registrations/attendance

Registrations 73 | Attendance 44

Method

Following an initial presentation, attendees participated in 2 interactive discussions described below. Participants were provided with an overview of the workshop and discussion topics prior to attending.

1. Group Discussion - What is the national portfolio of health cohort studies we should be creating?

Participants were asked the following questions via a Mentimeter poll. The facilitator invited some participants to speak to their responses to provide additional information.

- Should we prioritise some types of cohort study (e.g. population vs disease) over others? If so, why?
- Are there specific studies we should target? In your opinion, why are these ones a priority?
- Are there other kinds of selection criteria that should be considered?

2. Breakout Session - What is our reason and approach for doing measure-level discovery?

Participants were asked the following questions in small group breakout rooms. Responses were captured in a shared Google Doc.

- Benefits of measure-level discovery: What are some examples of the research activity you're undertaking that are helped by measure-level discovery and how does it help? How is this more helpful than study or dataset-level discovery?
- National requirements for measure-level discovery: If you had a national-level view of cohort study data, what are the measure-level search terms or filters you'd use to narrow down your search results?
- Existing standards: What are the existing measure-level discovery standards that we should consider? For example, are there existing platforms that do measure-level discovery well? What is your reason for recommending them?
- Optional question (if time allows) Can you apply the same measure-level approach to both population and disease-based cohorts? Please include examples if you have any.

Workshop 3

Purpose

The 3rd workshop sought feedback to inform ARDC's decisions on the following:

- To discuss what needs to be included to create a holistic and valuable program of work
- To discuss different partnership & infrastructure models we could consider

Date

27 Aug 2024

Registrations/attendance

Registrations 78 | Attendance 34

Method

Following an initial presentation, attendees participated in 2 interactive discussions described below. Participants were provided with an overview of the workshop and discussion topics prior to attending.

1. **Breakout Session - What needs to be included to make a well-rounded, high value national cohort data initiative?**

Participants were asked the following questions in small group breakout rooms. Responses were captured in a shared Google Doc.

- What are the other activities that should be included in a national health cohorts data initiative?
 - Enabling activities: Simply building systems and technology is not enough to ensure a complex issue like data sharing can be addressed. To create a more holistic program, what other activities could we undertake to help facilitate data sharing?
 - Upstream/downstream activities: Data sharing happens at a specific stage in the research/data lifecycle. Are there systems or other things that occur at different stages of the lifecycle that, if addressed, could help facilitate data sharing?
- How do we ensure the program provides value for its partners?
 - Creating a national cohort data initiative that provides value for a range of partners can be challenging given that cohort studies are at different levels of maturity. For example, cataloguing data might be limited and of lower value for some cohorts, but a significant challenge for others to address. What aspects of a national data initiative would provide the most value for your cohort(s)?

2. Group Discussion - What partnership & infrastructure model(s) should be considered?

Participants were asked the following questions as part of a moderated discussion. The facilitator invited participants to speak and provide their perspectives. The session was recorded for note-taking purposes.

- Will the current Node partnerships be able to support a national health cohorts data initiative?
 - For our existing Nodes: What kind of model did you have in mind for partnering with cohorts?
 - For those who can't (or would prefer not to) partner with an existing Node: Why wouldn't this option work for you? Can you work together with multiple new partners as a Node? Will you be able to provide the functions of a Node?
- Participants were shown the image below and asked to discuss their perspective on the options for enriched cohort data discovery which the facilitator framed as:
 - BUILD (Option 1 from the image): Heavily modify Health Data Australia to support cohorts
 - ADOPT (Option 2 from the image): ARDC purchases existing data discovery software and runs it on behalf of the health cohorts community
 - ADAPT (Option 2 from the image): ARDC co-invests in the uplift of an existing cohort data platform so that it can support and be utilised by the broader health cohorts community

Image: options for enriched cohort data discovery

FEEDBACK & INSIGHTS

Participant feedback was reviewed by ARDC and synthesised as follows. The synthesised feedback from workshop 1 and 2 was presented to participants at the subsequent workshop to validate ARDC's interpretation. Feedback from the final workshop has been summarised below and will be validated in subsequent discussions with stakeholders and potential project partners.

Strategic considerations for a national health cohort data initiative

Research uses & value of a national health cohort data catalogue

Secondary uses of shared cohort data, including uses of data pooled across multiple multiple cohorts:

- Linkage projects
- Population-based studies
- Large scale epidemiological and genetic studies
- Cohorts across different regions
- Baseline information for basic science projects
- Cross-cohort analyses
- Health economics studies
- Validation of survey instruments in other cohorts

Research uses & value of combining clinical trial and health cohort data:

- Cohorts can provide baseline data for trial developments
- Cohort studies can leverage existing clinical trial study outcomes
- Nested clinical trials within cohort studies
- Assess the impact of lifestyle factors on chronic disease outcomes

Key stakeholders

- Big national cohorts
- Existing metadata platforms
- Ethics committees
- Universities and/or faculties
- Consumers
- Other NCRIS organisations
- Research peak national bodies
- Industry (e.g. pharma, biotech)*

- State reps / health services

*There was not consensus about the appropriateness or prioritisation of industry as a key stakeholder

Priorities and criteria for creating a national portfolio of health cohort studies

Participants suggested different approaches for setting priorities for the portfolio which included:

- Alignment with other national strategies and priority areas (e.g. in health, society, education, etc).
- Nationally representative
- Potential impact on public health and healthcare
- International relevance and comparison
- Large and small cohorts (e.g. long running cohorts, rare conditions (to support sample size), etc)

Participants also identified different criteria for the selection of individual cohort studies for inclusion. These were:

Data

- Multiple kinds of data (e.g. survey, biomarker, etc)
- Data completeness and quality
- Data approved for third party use

Partners

- Potential for collaboration
- Adequate resources / preparedness to partner

Program scope, value, & enabling activities

To support the program's goal of facilitating data sharing by developing a national platform to support discovery of Australian health cohort studies and their data assets, participants suggested the following:

- ARDC must consider existing cohort infrastructure and data sharing practices, and should aim to extend existing capability as opposed to replacing it
- New national infrastructure should have a purpose and value that is distinct from existing cohort infrastructure
- A national initiative could enable knowledge sharing and research efficiency by establishing a communication network across Australian cohorts. Such a network, or community of practice, could allow cohorts to share successful research data practices, and/or facilitate the development of more standardised practices where required.
- To be sustainable, new innovation must align with the strategy of partner institutions and require minimal changes in practice by researchers/cohorts whose ability to change practice will be constrained by research funding limitations.

- Establishing early awareness and buy-in from a range of stakeholders (general public, cohort participants, researchers, research organisations, funders, ethics committees) is essential and should complement existing activities
- In addition to benefiting researchers, value needs to be proven at the institutional level to maintain buy-in and generate policy and cultural change and support
- To facilitate data sharing, different resources may be required for legacy/existing cohorts vs new/future cohorts. Resources to make data sharing a standard practice for future studies may not benefit legacy cohorts who will need to navigate (or negotiate) existing governance arrangements (e.g. ethics, partnership arrangements, etc) and data management practices.
- The establishment of a national register of health cohort studies (akin to the ANZCTR for Australian clinical trials) could be considered
- Suggestions of specific resources that could be developed include guidance on:
 - Collaboration protocols
 - Access management
 - Agreements for multi-institutional studies
 - Standards for data dictionaries
 - Data sharing policy
 - Data sharing contract template
 - Standardisation of data request forms
 - Standards for measure-level data (i.e. to support data standardisation/harmonisation)

Practical considerations for developing a national data discovery platform for health cohorts

Information requirements

Participant feedback suggested:

- In general, the kinds of study- and dataset-metadata collected about clinical trials is also relevant, however specific items require further consideration
- There are some existing metadata standards developed by some organisations, but no dominant standards across cohorts
- Most cohorts collect some of the metadata we discussed in a digital format, but there is variation in the quantity of information captured, the formats used to capture information, and the ease of updating that information

Key activities

Participants confirmed that the following activities proposed by ARDC are appropriate:

- Build stakeholder consensus on information needs of researcher searching for health cohort data
- Design metadata standards to meet the user information needs that could be implemented by health cohort studies and/or their organisations
- Design & build systems and processes within studies/organisations to deliver metadata to Health Data Australia
- Deliver metadata records to Health Data Australia

In addition, participants suggested the following be considered:

Outreach

- Improve awareness of existing cohort studies
- User engagement & training
- Stakeholder engagement
- Early engagement with users
- Educational approach on how to design study for sharing from the start.
- A “roadshow” activities for awareness, education
- Develop consensus and buy-in, increase engagement and culture change

Infrastructure design & outputs

- Develop templates for data access and sharing agreement, standard operating procedures, governance
- Recognition of work required to prepare data for sharing
- Big longitudinal studies needed as basis from which cross-sectional research can be performed

Key contributors

Participants identified the following types of contributor that would need to be involved in project teams:

Data specialists

- Data managers with skills in: data mapping and harmonisation, metadata standards
- Data custodians

Researchers

- Cohort linkage partners
- Project/research managers

Technical specialists

- IT support

Governance groups

- Research office support
- Ethics committees
- Legal/ contracts offices

Outreach teams

- Comms
- Training

Considerations for national scale measure-level discovery

Benefits of measure-level discovery

- Improves the efficiency of search / data discovery
- Determine if measures are relevant / irrelevant for a given secondary research project
- Can inform planning of analyses
- Can help identify if data from different cohorts be combined / harmonised
- Allows data requests to be more precise and focused on relevant, appropriate data
- Can inform new study design (e.g. by using similar measures)
- Reduce the amount of enquiries for more details

Informatics approach & standards

When asked about existing measure-level informatics approaches, participants predominantly identified controlled terminologies and vocabularies such as:

- ABS standards (e.g. sex/gender classification)
- MeSH
- ICD
- Australian Health Data Dictionary
- OMOP
- SNOMED
- BIDS

This unearthed a discussion about how “measure-level” should be defined (noting that the idea of measure-level discovery originated in [original consultations with the health cohorts community](#)). To this end, a hierarchy for describing health cohort outcome measures was used to facilitate further discussion. This hierarchy is based on work done by the Lifecourse initiative:

- Domain level (e.g. Mental health)
 - Construct level (e.g. Depression)

→ Measure level (e.g. K10 questionnaire)

→ Variable level (e.g. K10, question 7 - “About how often did you feel depressed?”)

Using this frame of reference, participants suggested that a national platform should support data discovery at construct or measure level at a minimum.

Partnership & infrastructure models

The final discussion on partnership and infrastructure models did not result in clear consensus on a preferred partnership or infrastructure model. However it did confirm some principles that emerged throughout the consultation process:

- A key benefit of the program would be to establish a national network or community of health cohorts to share and/or work towards common data practices - since no such community exists
- Mature, respected cohort discovery services already exist within a few health research areas. These services provide excellent granularity WRT measure-level discovery and provide notable coverage within their respective areas. However there is currently no service that provides a broader national view of health cohorts in Australia.
- If HeSANDA wishes to establish a national measure-level discovery service, it would be sensible to leverage an existing service as long as it could be developed to support a broader set of cohorts. At a minimum, there is not a compelling case to build a new measure-level discovery service from scratch.
- For clinical trials, HeSANDA has established a strong national partnership of research organisations. Opportunities to leverage this for health cohorts should be pursued. If there are high-value cohort studies that could not be supported by the current national partnerships, then new partnerships should be considered.

CONCLUSIONS

As per the [program guidelines](#), the aims of the program are to:

- Develop a national platform to support discovery of Australian health cohort studies and their data assets
- Develop a national community of practice to support Australian health cohort study data practices and culture
- Develop community-agreed national metadata standards for health cohort studies
- Uplift the consistency of data policies and practices across health cohort studies

The feedback received during the workshops confirmed support for these program aims and refined the outcomes for projects established under the program. These aims include:

1. Creation of a national inclusive network of health cohort studies to enable knowledge sharing and the sharing/development of resources to improve and standardise research data management practices
2. Develop the capability for the network to make their data discoverable in ARDC's existing national health data catalogue (Health Data Australia) to improve the visibility of their research and drive new collaborations. Here the aim would be for a good coverage of research cohorts with regularly updated high-level descriptions of data holdings and data request processes.

Note: The catalogue will not replace existing cohort data catalogues or platforms but will:

- a. Enable data discovery for cohorts that existing platforms do not support
 - b. Enable national-level visibility for cohorts already supported by platforms
3. Develop this network and its capability by extending existing HeSANDA node arrangements where possible. If the existing nodes can not establish partnerships which provide national coverage of health cohorts, then consider the establishment of new cohort nodes where feasible.
 4. Establish a national measure-level data discovery platform for cohorts (or 'cohort explorer') to enable more detailed and bespoke cohort discovery. The cohort explorer platform would complement Health Data Australia's broad and general discovery of data for health research. The cohort explorer would focus on a subset of cohorts with high re-use potential and apply a much more fine-grained harmonisation of metadata, enabling deeper cross-cohort exploration. ARDC should aim to leverage existing mature platforms for this purpose.